

Light-Powered Self-Adaptive Mesostructured Microrobots for Simultaneous Microplastics Trapping and Fragmentation via in situ Surface Morphing

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Microplastics, which comprise one of the omnipresent threats to human health, are diverse in shape and composition. Their negative impacts on human and ecosystem health provide ample incentive to design and execute strategies to trap and degrade diversely structured microplastics, especially from water. This work demonstrates the fabrication of single-component TiO₂ superstructured microrobots to photo-trap and photo-fragment microplastics. In a single reaction, rod-like microrobots diverse in shape and with multiple trapping sites, are fabricated to exploit the asymmetry of the microrobotic system advantageous for propulsion. The microrobots work synergistically to photo-catalytically trap and fragment microplastics in water in a coordinated fashion. Hence, a microrobotic model of “unity in diversity” is demonstrated here for the phototrapping and photofragmentation of microplastics. During light irradiation and subsequent photocatalysis, the surface morphology of microrobots transformed into porous flower-like networks that trap microplastics for subsequent degradation. This reconfigurable microrobotic technology represents a significant step forward in the efforts to degrade microplastics.

1. Introduction

Humans' increased consumption of plastic products endangers the environment and, hence, living organisms.^[1] Plastic bottles, food packaging, and plastic bags are major sources of microplastics (MPs) that contaminate the environment. MPs can enter the human body by inhalation and ingestion, causing cell damage or inflammation and immune reactions.^[2] This statement corroborates several recent studies, especially one that detected MPs in human blood.^[3] Among the 22 human blood samples under study, 17 were contaminated with MPs. Of those 17 blood samples, half contained polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which is commonly used in the manufacture of plastic drink bottles, and one-third contained polystyrene (PS), which is used in food packaging. One-quarter of the 17 blood samples contained polyethylene (PE), the most commonly used polymer used to make plastic bags.^[3] In addition to the bloodstream, MPs have also been detected in human feces.^[4] Indeed, it has also been

reported that MPs can be absorbed by organs and even cells, and thereby leading to the effects of carcinogenicity, chronic toxicity, genotoxicity, and developmental toxicity.^[5,6] These findings reveal how MPs in the environment dangerously perturb the rhythm of life on Earth. At current growth rates, 12000 Mt of plastic waste is expected to be dumped in the environment by 2050, highlighting the *sine qua non* for effective strategies to degrade such plastics in the water in their micro and nano forms.^[1] Importantly, nanoplastics can penetrate more easily into living organisms, causing more severe problems. It is therefore necessary to degrade microplastics completely. Conventional methods to remove plastics, e.g., incineration, are inappropriate due to environmental constraints. Hence, a green and eco-friendly advanced oxidation process, photocatalysis, has come into focus and has received prime attention for the purpose of degrading organic pollutants, including microplastics.^[7–9]

Photocatalysis is one of the most effective and efficient strategies to degrade organic pollutants to form ideally products such as CO₂ and H₂O.^[10,11] It is the process in which the acceleration of a reaction occurs when a material, usually a semiconductor, interacts with light to produce the reactive oxygen species (ROS)

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that promote the photocatalytic transformation of pollutants.^[10] Typically, the oxidation of dissociatively adsorbed H₂O by photo-generated holes takes place and the simultaneous reduction of an electron acceptor (generally the dissolved oxygen or oxygen vacancies) by photo-excited electrons occurs. These reactions lead to the generation of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals (OH[•] and O₂^{•-}) that eventually interact with the pollutant to induce photodegradation.^[10,11] Recently, microplastic photodegradation has received wide attention and researchers have successfully implemented this method to degrade various pollutants.^[7] Materials such as ZnO,^[12] BiOCl,^[13] BiOBr,^[14] and TiO₂^[15] are some of the photocatalysts used. Among these, TiO₂ has been the favorite among scientists due to its chemical stability, nontoxicity, and low cost.^[16] For a photocatalyst to be more active, a large specific area and, hence, an enormous number of reaction sites and enough surface sites for the multiple reflection of photons are necessary. Because all these advantages are applicable for mesocrystal superstructures, they have been utilized in photocatalysis with excellent results after the first report on mesocrystals and periodic superstructures by Colfen et al.^[17] Along with TiO₂,^[18] Cu₂O,^[19] Ta₂O₅,^[20] ZnCo₂O₄,^[21] and ZnO,^[22] mesocrystal photocatalysts have also been reported to outperform their conventional variants. All the aforementioned non-motile photocatalysts under light illumination had to be mechanically or magnetically stirred along with the pollutant system in order to improve the ability to attack and further degrade pollutants.^[23,24] If a light-propelled micro/nanorobot is replaced by such photocatalysts, then energy consumption can be reduced for performing photocatalytic trapping and degradation.^[25–31] It is also worth noting that in addition to light-propelled micro/nanorobots, magnetic micro/nanorobots have also played an invaluable role in soft robotics, with an emphasis on environmental and biomedical applications.^[32–34]

Our group has developed a Pt-Pd/hematite Janus structure to fragment polymers; for example, high-molecular mass PEG was photofragmented under UV irradiation.^[35] We demonstrated that we can digest and decompose various solid polymers using BiVO₄ and Bi₂WO₆ microrobots.^[36,37] Furthermore, an MXene-derived γ -Fe₂O₃/Pt/TiO₂ microrobot was developed to photocatalytically trap nanoplastics.^[38] Recently, TiO₂ micromotors have been developed for the removal of microplastics and suspended matter.^[39] In addition to TiO₂, BiVO₄ has also been found to be a strong candidate to capture and degrade polylactic acid and polycaprolactone to smaller oligomers and polymers.^[24,40] In light of all these experiments, we explored the cooperative schooling/clustering mechanism of micro/nanomotors in microplastics degradation.^[24,40] In this type of motion, the micro/nanomotors are seen as clusters or schools, and upon light illumination they propel away from the central point of their corresponding clusters.^[41–43] When the illumination is turned off, the micromachines move back to their original position.^[44] Such behavior is mostly seen for TiO₂ and has been used in cargo transport.^[44–46] Unlike single microrobots, a cluster of microrobots itself could perform as an untethered intelligent robot and its schooling behavior used to attack the surrounding pollutants. In addition, not only the surface of each micro/nanorobot but also the space between two or more of them can also act as traps for pollutants. To the best of our knowledge, no reports are available showing the photocatalytic trapping and degradation of mi-

croplastics using TiO₂ single-component microrobots. Herein, we have developed a new strategy for the synthesis of asymmetric single-component superstructured TiO₂ microrobots and a unique in situ surface morphology transformation pathway capable of phototrapping and photofragmenting microplastics in water (Scheme 1).

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Fabrication of TiO₂ Microrobots

The hydrothermal treatment of the precursor solution containing an equimolar concentration (5 mmol) of TiOSO₄, hexamethylene tetramine (HMT), and NaOH was nucleated by thermodynamic force, reducing the total surface energy of the resulting structure, which had ripened into asymmetric superstructures with rod-like morphology.^[47] As shown in Figure 1A, the Ti precursor self-assembled in the solution followed by anisotropic growth. These anisotropically grown structures can undergo Ostwald ripening to fabricate TiO₂ mesocrystal microrobots. Considering previous reports that high hydroxyl concentration can induce schooling mechanisms, NaOH is used as an hydroxyl source.^[46,48,49] XRD results show that the synthesized TiO₂ superstructure is in the anatase phase, which is considered the most suitable phase for photocatalysis (Figure 1B) due to its wide band gap energy, which enables it to minimize electron-hole recombination.^[50] The peaks of Ti2p XPS (Figure 1C) at 457.1 and 458.5 eV correspond to Ti2p_{3/2}, and the peaks at 464.3 and 461.8 eV belong to Ti2p_{1/2}.^[51] The peaks at 457.1 and 461.8 eV are attributed to the presence of Ti³⁺ at the surface of TiO₂ in addition to the Ti⁴⁺ peaks at 458.5 and 464.3 eV. These findings prove that Ti³⁺ self-doping occurred on the surface of TiO₂, which is beneficial for reducing electron-hole recombination by tailing the conduction band minimum.^[52] Furthermore, O1s XPS shows three peaks viz. 529.8, 530.7, and 531.4 eV, corresponding to Ti–O–Ti, Ti–OH, and surface-adsorbed H₂O, respectively (Figure 2D).^[53] The survey XPS is shown in Figure S1A (Supporting Information). The synthesized anatase TiO₂ microrobots possessed rod-like morphology with diameters in the range of 1–3 μ m, where their building units are in nano-dimension. This superstructure morphology is revealed from SEM images shown in Figure 1E–G. A low-magnification SEM image is also shown in Figure S1B (Supporting Information). In Figure 1F, the end parts of superstructures are irregular and the constituent primary building blocks of the superstructures are displayed in Figure 1G. Moreover, these superstructures possessed an appreciable surface area of 182 m² g⁻¹ (Figure S2A, Supporting Information) and mesoporous nature (Figure S2B, Supporting Information), which is highly beneficial for the diffusion of large quantities of organic pollutants and, thereby, photocatalytic degradation.^[54]

2.2. Motion Experiments

Motion experiments were carried out in the presence and absence of 0.5% H₂O₂ as fuel. The synthesized TiO₂ mesocrystal microrobots have shown expansion (UV on)/schooling (UV off) behavior, which has received considerable attention and

Scheme 1. General outline of the phototrapping and photofragmentation of microplastics in aqueous media using superstructured TiO₂ microrobots.

Figure 1. A) Mechanism of formation of superstructured TiO₂ microrobots and their B) XRD, C) Ti2p XPS, D) O1s XPS, E) low-resolution SEM, F) SEM showing highly disordered surface, and G) high-resolution SEM showing constituent nano-building blocks of TiO₂ microrobots.

is useful in the context of swarm robotics and biomimetic materials.^[45,48,55,56] The mechanism is well explained in very recent publications.^[45,48] The spontaneous clustering of microrobots occurs in the dark due to the dissociation and diffusion of protons from the TiO₂ surface and the resulting electroosmosis. The expansion of the cluster, on the other hand, is due to the decomposition of H₂O₂ and the resulting O₂ concentration gradient.^[57] The motion behavior is observed for our mi-

cro-robots even in the absence of H₂O₂ and could be attributed to the asymmetric morphology of the mesostructures and the photo-generated chemical species that can generate a chemical pressure around each microrobot to generate an electric field to propel them (Video S1). To explain the mechanism, the photo-generated electrons on UV illumination can react with oxygen in the media and H₂O₂ fuel to generate reactive oxygen species such as OH[•] and O₂^{-•} while the photo-generated holes are able

Figure 2. A) Microscopic images of the expansion–contraction mechanism of TiO_2 microrobots during motion experiments using 0.5% H_2O_2 under UV on–off conditions (scale bar 10 μm). B) Images of the expansion–contraction mechanism of TiO_2 microrobots during motion experiments in the presence of polystyrene using 0.5% H_2O_2 under UV on–off conditions (scale bar is 5 μm).

to oxidize water into OH^{\bullet} or decompose H_2O_2 into protons and oxygen. The asymmetric rod morphology of TiO_2 microrobots leads to the asymmetrical photogeneration of chemical ions. The photo-generated ions diffuse at different rates, creating a local electrical field and a chemical pressure around the motor that make the charged particles expand the cluster.^[42,44,45] In the microrobot system with H_2O_2 , the expansion–schooling was more prominent as shown in Figure 2A. The microrobot cluster ($t = 0$) started expanding under UV illumination. After 7 s, when the UV light is turned off, the cluster moves in the opposite direction and returns almost back to its original state after 20 s (Video S2).^[58] A video showing the wide view of the microrobots is presented as Video S3. Changes in the mean inter-robotic distances of this cluster during this UV light on–off mechanism are shown in Figure S3 (Supporting Information), which presents a rather rudimentary example of such quantitative analysis. It is also worth noting that the weakly bound nano building blocks of the superstructures contain spaces between them. These interparticle spaces at the surface of the microrobots likely prompt multiple reflections of UV photons, thereby allowing more efficient use of light energy and triggering propulsion.^[59] Different trapping sites are available on the surface of microrobots and different modes of trapping before UV illumination are shown in Figure 3. These weak pre-trapping modes can reduce the freedom of microplastics to contaminate the solution. These weak interactions can cause the microplastic to be detached from the surface when the UV light is switched on. Evidence can easily be perceived from Video S4 and Video S5, and motion pictures (Figure 2B) where the mixture of TiO_2 and PS was studied in the presence of H_2O_2 .

2.3. Polystyrene Trapping

Plentiful trapping sites are present on the surface of superstructured TiO_2 microrobots as evident from the SEM images in Figure 3. Before UV irradiation, the PS particles are weakly trapped at the cracks, terminal ends, shallow surfaces, fused structures, layers, and curved shallow surfaces. Nearly all these weak interactions of PS with diverse TiO_2 microrobot surfaces may detach when UV irradiation is initiated as shown in Figure 2B and Video S4 and S5. When TiO_2 microrobots were used, the nanoseeds or primary nano building units of microrobots were deposited on the surface of PS beads (Figure 4A,B). As a control, we irradiated PS beads in the absence of any microrobots. The smooth surface characteristic was retained even after 12 h of UV irradiation as shown (inset) in between Figure 4A,B. It was expected that the PS trapping would be a herculean task in this scenario since light energy activates the detachment of PS from the microrobot surface rather than trapping. Surprisingly, as UV irradiation progressed, the nanoseed array on the microrobotic surface gradually transformed into petal-like architectures. On further illumination, the petals were more tightly interconnected to form a porous flower-like network where the petals were curly. In other words, the adjacent curly petals were self-organized via an oriented attachment (OA) mechanism.^[60] The vacant spaces available in between the curly fragments present on the transformed TiO_2 microrobot surface then trap polystyrene to competently commence the degradation process as evident from Figure 4C–F. In the crystal growth process here, it is expected that the nano building blocks of mesocrystal superstructures are accompanied by traces of HMT that can decompose at a tem-

Figure 3. SEM images of TiO₂ microrobots after being mixed with polystyrene beads before UV irradiation with different types of trapping at A) cracks, B) terminal ends, C) shallow surfaces, D) fused structures, E) layers, and F) curved surfaces (scale bar 500 nm).

Figure 4. SEM images showing TiO₂ microrobots' surface morphology transformation after 12 h UV irradiation in the PS microplastic model: A,B) TiO₂ fragments-decorated PS in the absence of H₂O₂ (inset shows PS alone after UV irradiation); C,D) PS photo-trapped at the flower-like network on TiO₂ microrobot surface (using 0.5% H₂O₂); E,F) magnified images of PS photo-trapped within the TiO₂ flower-like network (using 0.5% H₂O₂). Scale bar 500 nm.

perature between 200 and 300 °C, which is lower than the reaction temperature of 150 °C.^[61] Hence, some of the building units are attached together via the interaction of HMT. It is reported that H₂O₂ (the fuel used during phototrapping) is efficient in removing templates and organic functionalities, creating high surface area and porosity.^[62] This might have led the way to the surface morphology transformation on the microrobots' surface.

It has been reported that in the OA mechanism, solid particles with common crystallographic orientations can form larger aggregates by effective collisions between them.^[60] This is obvious here as the microrobots propelling under UV irradiation can facilitate effective collisions to facilitate the OA mechanism.^[60,63,64] The nature of each subunit of flower-like networks can empower them to enhance the multiple reflections of UV as well as sites

Figure 5. MALDI results of PEG fragmentation: A) PEG (control); B) PEG after 12 h UV irradiation; C) PEG + TiO₂ microrobots after 12 h UV irradiation.

for microplastics to commence photodegradation. The plausible mechanism of PS trapping is illustrated in Figure S1 (Supporting Information).

2.4. Polyethylene Glycol Degradation

Due to their expansion–schooling behavior and their capability of *in-situ* surface morphology transformation, TiO₂ microrobots can perform as ideal micromachines for effectively trapping a greater number of microplastics with the aim of degradation. Polyethylene glycol (PEG-4000) polymer is used as the microplastic model to evaluate and understand the fragmentation of polymers by TiO₂ microrobots. PEG-4000 was chosen instead of polystyrene as it has well defined mass and the resulting fragments are easily characterized by MALDI-TOF as PEG interacts with the surface of TiO₂ microrobots. PEG samples with TiO₂ in the presence and absence of 0.5% H₂O₂ and a PEG sample alone were exposed to UV irradiation for 12 h. PEG alone was set as a control to compare with and evaluate the photocatalytic effect of microrobots. **Figure 5** depicts the MALDI-MS spectra of PEG, UV irradiated PEG, and microrobots-treated PEG in the presence and absence of h⁺, O₂^{•-}, and •OH scavengers.^[65,66] Signals corresponding to PEG macromolecular chains around 4000 mass stay intact even after exposure to UV light (Figure 5A,B). While analyzing the MALDI of PEG treated with TiO₂ microrobots with 0.5% H₂O₂ as fuel in the photocatalytic system, a high rate of fragmentation is observed with intensity traces of microplastics at ≈1000 (Figure 5C). These results reveal that the microrobots have potentially photo-fragmented PEG to a greater extent after 12 h of UV exposure and that prolonged irradiation can lead to complete photocatalytic degradation. Furthermore, the MALDI of PEG treated with TiO₂ microrobots in the absence of H₂O₂ has also been carried out and it was found the signal intensities at the higher mass region are reduced to more than half and new peaks at lower mass are generated with the highest mass intensities observed at the mass region 750–1000 (Figure S4, Supporting Information). To determine the influence of reactive oxygen species (ROS), scavenger experiments have also been done using EDTA,

benzoquinone, and isopropanol as h⁺, O₂^{•-}, and •OH scavengers, respectively. The MALDI results after scavenger experiments are also shown in the same order from Figure S5A–S5C (Supporting Information). It can be easily perceived that all the ROS, including holes, have taken part in the photodegradation of PEG. While considering the high-intensity peak region (m/z 3200–5200) of bare PEG (Figure 5A,B), the intensity reduction is high for the hole scavenger EDTA (Figure S5A, Supporting Information) compared to the O₂^{•-} scavenger benzoquinone (Figure S5B, Supporting Information). The intensity in that specific region was highest when •OH scavenger isopropanol (Figure S5C, Supporting Information) was used. This proves that for PEG photodegradation using TiO₂ microrobots, •OH plays the dominant role compared to O₂^{•-} and h⁺. In a photocatalytic process, electron-hole pairs are generated as a result of UV irradiation. Due to the mesoporous nature and high surface area of TiO₂ microrobots presented here, it is easy for H₂O₂ and organic molecules (here PEG) to diffuse into the microrobot's mesoporous structure. These microrobots and H₂O₂ systems can be accelerated to generate OH[•] under UV irradiation at the expense of e⁻ and O₂^{•-} as shown in Equation (1) and (2).^[67]

These reactions may induce high concentrations of OH[•], which play a key role in undergoing random chain scission processes to yield oligomers and the lower molecular weight fragmentation products of PEG.^[68] To determine the capability of TiO₂ alone for the formation of •OH, a coumarin fluorescent probe method was employed, where the formation of 7-Hydroxycoumarin (fluorescence peak at 450 nm) is monitored (and, hence, OH[•] formation) at certain time intervals.^[69] It is evident from Figure S6 (Supporting Information) that the formation of OH[•] is highly possible even in the absence of fuel. Despite the high •OH concentration, the photodegradation ability of TiO₂ is far less compared to the same system containing H₂O₂. It proves that abilities such as the motion and high concentration of ROS formation (especially •OH) synergistically paved the way for the high rate of photodegradation of PEG. It is also worth mentioning that unlike in the case of PS trapping, the PEG degradation process does not result in flower-like trapping sites *in situ*. However, some distorted spherical-like aggregates are formed instead (Figure S7, Supporting Information). This may be because PEG and its low-molar mass derivatives are very well-known structure-directing agents to synthesize spherical-like aggregates of materials.^[70]

3. Conclusions

A single-component rod-like TiO₂ superstructure with self-propulsion ability has been developed. These autonomous superstructured microrobots possess the capability of *in situ* surface morphology transformation to transform the surface with a nanoseed array into flower-like architectures. These flower-like architectures on the surface facilitate photocatalytic trapping of polystyrene into the vacant spaces available between the curly

constructions present. Furthermore, we have demonstrated the photodegradation of high-molecular weight polyethylene glycol. The characterization using MALDI-MS confirmed that the polymer was photodegraded into its lower-mass compounds. Hence, this work advances the understanding of synthesizing single-component asymmetric superstructure microrobots of TiO₂ for phototrapping and photodegradation of microplastics as well as other suspended pollutants in water.

4. Experimental Section

Fabrication of TiO₂ Superstructured Microrobots: 5 mmol titanium oxy-sulfate (TiOSO₄) (0.7996 g) was added to a 50 mL solution of 5 mmol hexamethylene tetramine (HMT) (0.7009 g) and magnetically stirred for 1 h at 1500 rpm. To it was added 25 mL of 5 mmol NaOH solution (0.2 g) and stirring continued for another 1 h at the same condition. The solution was then kept in an autoclave at 150 °C for 18 h. After cooling, the sample was dried at 100 °C for 4 h and then washed using centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 3 min continuously using 50 mL each of ethanol and DI water.

Characterization of TiO₂ Microrobots: A high-resolution scanning electron microscope (FEI Verios 460L) was used to characterize sample morphology and the size of the microrobots synthesized. All the microrobots were in the range 1–3 μm diameter, where the particle distribution was 8% in the 1–1.6 μm size range, 36% in the 1.6–2 μm size range, and 56% in the 2.2–3 μm size range. It was worth noting that most of the particles (72%) were in the 2–2.6 μm range. XRD was recorded using a Rigaku Smart-Lab 3 kW X-ray powder diffractometer equipped with Cu Kα (λ = 1.54 Å) radiation at 40 kV. The chemical composition of microrobots was examined by XPS (Kratos Analytical Axis Supra), using a monochromatic Al Kα (1486.7 eV) excitation source. All peaks were calibrated to the adventitious C 1s peak at 284.8 eV. XPS spectra fitting was done using CasaXPS software. BET surface area measurements were done using a 3P Micro 300 C1 3P (BET_ANAMET) surface area analyzer. Prior to measurements, 0.2 g of TiO₂ was degassed using pure N₂ stream at an elevated temperature viz. 60 min at 90 °C, followed by 240 min at 150 °C.

Motion Behavior of TiO₂ Microrobots: The light-powered motion of microrobots was recorded using a Nikon Ts2R inverted optical microscope equipped with a UV LED (CoolLED pE-100, 365 nm; spot diameter 1.1 mm) at 463 mW cm⁻² and a digital camera (Basler, acA1920-155uc). The mean distance between the particles was analyzed using ImageJ software. A certain particle at the center of a school was considered as the reference particle and the distance from it to the particles present at the outermost layer (which were in close proximity with identical distance) was monitored.

Polystyrene Phototrapping: To evaluate the phototrapping efficiency of microrobots, Polybead Sulfate Microspheres of 500 nm diameter were used, which contained 3.64 × 10¹¹ beads mL⁻¹. In the experiment, 1 drop (≈50 μL) of PS was mixed with 10 mL of water to form a PS colloidal solution. 1 mL each of PS colloidal solution and TiO₂ microrobot suspension (1 mg mL⁻¹) were mixed in the presence and absence of 0.5% H₂O₂ and then illuminated for 12 h using a UV-LED light source with wavelength 365 nm (9 W) and a spot diameter of 1.1 mm. The surface reconfiguration of TiO₂ microrobots and the resulting phototrapping of PS were confirmed using SEM.

Polyethylene Glycol Photodegradation: For the photodegradation of PEG (molecular weight = 4000, Alfa Aesar) under UV-light irradiation, 1 mL each of 1 mg of PEG-4000, 1 mg of microrobots, and 0.5% H₂O₂ were mixed. Similarly, 2 control samples were prepared: i) without adding microrobots and H₂O₂, and ii) with 1 mg mL⁻¹ bare TiO₂ microrobots. For the scavenger experiments, 20 mg mL⁻¹ EDTA, 5.5 μg mL⁻¹ benzoquinone, and 5 vol% of isopropanol were separately mixed with the photocatalytic system containing PEG, microrobots, and 0.5% H₂O₂. All solutions were prepared in a disposable cuvette and irradiated using a 365 nm UV LED for 12 h. After the photodegradation experiments, except for the control PEG solution, the other two were filtered using a membrane

with a pore diameter of 250 nm. The collected solutions were stored for further analysis. PEG-4000 degradation was analyzed using an Ultraflex-treme instrument (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) operated in linear positive ion detection mode. A three-layer sample preparation technique was used: a layer of 50 mg/mL trans-2-[3-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-2-2-methyl-2-propenylidene] malononitrile in acetone in a volume of 0.2 μL dried on a stainless-steel target overlaid with 0.2 μL of a saturated solution of NaI in acetone and then the with the sample solution (0.2 μL).

Coumarin Probe Method: For the coumarin photoluminescence probe method, 5 cuvettes containing 1 mL each of 1.4 mM coumarin solution, 1 mg of PEG-4000, and 1 mg of microrobots were set up under UV irradiation, and each of them underwent fluorescence measurements at different time intervals and were monitored for an increase in intensity of the peak corresponding to 7-Hydroxycoumarin (at ≈450 nm).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

S.G.U. designed and performed the fabrication and characterization of microrobots and carried out the analysis of motion and performed PS trapping and PEG photodegradation experiments. S.G.U. and M.P. conceived the idea. M.P. originated and supervised the research. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

TiO₂, surface morphology, microrobots, microplastics, micromotors

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